

A Novel Approach to Test Suite Prioritization Using Binary Insertion Sort

Hemant Kumar | Vipin Saxena

Department of Computer Science, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Vidya Vihar, Rae Bareli Road, Lucknow, India.

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KEYWORDS

Binary Insertion Sorting(BIS),
Software Products,
Software Testing,
Test Cases,
Test Suites.

ABSTRACT

Software testing is a crucial activity that is performed during the development of a software product to ensure its reliability, functionality, and overall quality. Without successful software testing, software products cannot be launched into the competitive software market, as undetected defects can lead to failures, financial losses, and security vulnerabilities. Furthermore, the performance of the various modules involved in software products depends significantly on the selection of optimized test cases. Efficient test case prioritization helps save execution time, reducing computational costs, and improving fault detection efficiency. Therefore, the present article focuses on the systematic selection of test cases, which are encapsulated into well-structured test suites, optimized, and prioritized using the Binary Insertion Sorting (BIS) technique. The proposed technique enhances the execution efficiency of the software product while improving Average Percentage of Fault Detection (APFD) and optimizing memory utilization over the selected test suites. Additionally, the technique is compared with existing methods available in the literature, and the computed results are presented comprehensively in the form of tables and graphs.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the software products is completed through various activities involved in the development phases in which software testing is one of the important phases having the life cycle. This shows that the test cases are encapsulated to form a test suite

which may be used to execute the module involved in the software product. Once the test suite is successfully executed over the module then may be destroyed after the use but when it is for no use for the module then it can be discarded. During the software testing, it is to be ensured that the systematic approach of software

testing fulfills the requirements given by the client and the produced product must be free from defects. The outcome as a software product must be of high quality and more reliable as per the needs of the client as well as the needs of the customers. Therefore, one can say that software testing is one of the crucial phases in the development of software products. But the question is whether the selected test cases are feasible or not and another is whether the test cases have been optimized and prioritized or not. On these aspects, some of the important research papers have been consulted and these are elaborated in brief before selecting the research problem which has been presented in this paper. In the year 2019, Ovidiu Baniias [1] employed a memorization dynamic programming technique to optimize the test case selection and to prioritize the test cases before use in the software testing. The outcome is a huge reduction in memory consumption, utilizing up to 400 times less memory in the best-case scenario and roughly 40 times less memory on average when compared to standard dynamic programming knapsack solutions. Shin et al. [2] expressed a test case prioritization method that combines diversity-based and mutation-based methodologies, with a focus on mutant distinguishment and conducted an empirical evaluation using 352 real mistakes and 553,477 developer-written test cases, looking at both standard mutant kill and mutant distinguishment criteria in single-objective greedy, hybrid, and multi-objective optimization settings. The results showed that there isn't a single dominating method that works for all kinds of defects. The variations and contextual factors are also described using the Mutant Distinguishment Graph (MDG).

In the year 2020, Mahdieha et al. [3] proposed an improvement method for fault-proneness estimations into coverage-based Test Case Prioritisation (TCP) techniques, which intends to improve the widely used additional strategy. By using software bugs, history is available to develop a neural network model and method-enabled fault-proneness estimation in code segments. Relevant bug histories have also been implemented which are significantly enhanced coverage-based approaches for TCP, as shown by an evaluation based on 357 versions of five real-world applications. Zhou et al. [4] proposed a dispersity

metric-based test case prioritization method based on pragmatic considerations like Random Prioritizing (RP). Empirical evaluations carried out on fifteen real-world projects revealed that the technique was more effective than RP. This technique allows to preservation of linear computational complexity while prioritizing sizable test suites with numerous test cases. Furthermore, it handles scenarios in which input-based or execution-based techniques cannot be applied due to data constraints. Lima and Vergilio [5] presented the COLEMAN approach, a Combinatorial VOLatile Multi-Armed BANDit based on Multi-Armed Bandit (MAB) methodologies, for TCP in Continuous Integration (CI) systems. It effectively controls the volatile and combinatorial nature of the TCPCI problem by adapting to the addition and removal of test cases over cycles. When compared to other literature techniques, COLEMAN performs better in early failure detection, as demonstrated by its evaluation across eleven systems and a range of time budgets.

In the year 2021, Qasim et al. [6] investigated TCP strategies in software regression testing by conducting a comprehensive literature review and identified various TCP solutions based on a number of parameters, including code alterations, needs, errors, execution time, and cost. The survey offers academics and practitioners a useful resource for studies completed between 2010 to 2021, but a more comprehensive analysis of the benefits and drawbacks of the approaches would enhance its practical utility. Bagherzadeh et al. [7] introduced Reinforcement Learning (RL) in the context of Continuous Integration (CI) for the first time introduced test case prioritizing as an RL job and used three ranking models. Using state-of-the-art RL approaches, the work aims at continuously learning optimality-approximating prioritization algorithms. The comprehensive and extended experiments produced findings that demonstrate RL's potential to achieve near-optimal test case prioritization in the context of Continuous Integration: top RL methods outperform earlier RL-based strategies in terms of accuracy.

In the year 2022, Mahdieha et al. [8] [2022] introduced a novel method for test case prioritizing that makes use of past bug data to determine fault-proneness in code

areas and test case diversification for better efficiency. A comprehensive study using datasets from five real-world projects (357 versions) showed that the approach outperformed traditional coverage-based TCP approaches, offering a means of extending test suites in software development. Pan et al. [9] examined 29 studies from 2006 to 2020 as part of a comprehensive evaluation of machine learning-based test case selection and prioritization (ML-based TSP) methods. Important research topics about ML-based TSP were covered in the review of work, including variances in methodology, training, and testing feature sets, assessment metrics, performance results, and study repeatability. In order to facilitate and better understanding of the developing topic, the study offers a succinct taxonomy for classifying upcoming ML-based TSP research. Ahmed et al. [10] examined 21 out of 165 papers that were selected using predefined criteria as part of a systematic evaluation of value-based, cost-aware TCP techniques and focused on algorithm use, performance measures, and validation methodologies in the analysis. Remarkably, algorithms were employed in twelve publications, primarily Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). Along with case studies, industrial case studies, and empirical research, experiments were a common way of validation. The report underscores the importance of integrating principles that are value-based and cost-aware into TCP and emphasizes the substantial research opportunities in this domain. Bajaj et al. [11] proposed an improved QPSO-based method for TCP that overcomes prior shortcomings and makes use of novel characteristics to increase effectiveness. Numerous research demonstrating its effectiveness in fault and statement coverage have proven its superiority over other TCP algorithms. A trade-off was seen during test case reduction: excellent fault coverage was offset by a 7% fault detection loss, indicating that regression testing necessitates balancing priorities. Ahmed et al. [12] investigated value-based cost-cognizant TCP techniques through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). PSO techniques, experiment-based outcomes validation, and the APFDc metric were found to be widely used. In the SLR, the importance of value-based TCP is highlighted, and future research directions are noted.

In the year 2023, Nazir et al. [13] developed MOPSO, which optimizes fault coverage, guarantees thorough test case coverage, and reduces execution time, to enable multi-objective test case prioritization in regression testing and demonstrated the superiority of MOPSO in the work, which employed APFD as the metric, by achieving an 85% fault coverage, better execution speed, and fault detection rates. Ufuktepe and Tuglular [14] invented LoM-Score, a test case prioritizing technique inspired by the law of minimal and used the Dissimilarity-LoM-Score (Dis-LoM-Score), which enhanced with the help of Jaccard Similarity. In a case study including ten Java projects, Dis-LoM-Score effectively reduced method redundancy by providing better regression testing efficiency and surpassing other techniques in terms of Average Percentage of Faults Detected (APFD). Kumar, H., and Saxena, V. [15], introduce HRT, a hybrid Harmony Search and RBF-NN method, for automated test case generation. HRT optimizes branch coverage and fault detection, outperforming traditional algorithms in software testing. Kumar, H., and Saxena, V. [16], present a novel test case generation method integrating Harmony Search (HS) with mutation analysis. This approach enhances test case diversity and fault detection, demonstrated through improved coverage and mutation scores, showcasing its potential for efficient software testing.

Based on the above work, it is observed from the literature that the Binary Insertion Sort [17] has never been used by the researchers for optimization and prioritization of the test cases which may be used for effective software testing strategies that produce efficient software products. The technique covers the generation of test cases which are grouped in terms of test suits, optimized, and prioritized based on the size of the test suits through the concept of the binary insertion sort.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

After an exhaustive review of the literature available on the optimization and prioritization of the test cases used to develop efficient software products, it is observed that researchers and scientists have never used the concept of the Binary Insertion Sort which involves the binary search for prioritization of the test

cases which are encapsulated in the form of test suites. Initially, a large volume of the software product development through Python programming language is considered, thereafter, the test cases are formulated and grouped together to form the test suites. The test suites are arranged in increasing order using the binary insertion sort technique and if one wants to find the selected test cases, then it can be obtained through a binary search algorithm.

2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The test cases are grouped together and defined as test suites and the software product consists of the many modules which must produce efficient results over the selected test suits. For this purpose, a system model is designed and represented below:

Figure 1. A System Model

A. Software Product

A software product is a combination of the modules which may be dependent or independent modules represented as $SP = \{MD_1, MD_2, \dots, MD_l\}$, where l is controlling a total number of modules. In this case, the size of modules may or may not differ from each other.

B. Test Suite

A test suite is defined as a set of distinct test cases or scenarios used to evaluate the functionality, performance, reliability, and durability of the software product. It helps to find bugs, errors, faults, and variations from the expected behavior by carefully examining and validating the software product. A test suite can be mathematically represented as follows:

$$T = (S, R, O, M, RE) \quad (1)$$

Where, T , S , O , R , M , and RE are Test Suite, Set of test cases, Set of expected outcomes, Mapping function ($R: S \rightarrow O$), *Metadata and Rules for execution of test cases, respectively. An example of a test suit for login functionality is given below:

Test Case	Description	Expected Outcome	Metadata	Rules for Execution
1	login successfully with a valid username and password.	The user is redirected to the dashboard.	Test data: valid username and valid password	Execute this test case initially.

C. Binary Insertion Sort Algorithm

Let us first define the binary search algorithm which works over the size of the test suit/module. In the algorithm, the size of the test suit is stored in an array of $A[1..N]$, while LI and UI are the lower index and upper index values, respectively. The algorithm works up to when the value of LI is equal to UI . By the use of this algorithm, the size of test suits/modules may be sorted in ascending order.

```
def binary_search(A, X, LI, UI):
```

```
    while LI < UI:
```

```
        mid = (LI + UI) // 2
```

```
        if A[mid]['num_of_testCase'] < x
```

```
            LI = mid + 1
```

```
        else:
```

```
            UI = mid
```

```
    return UI
```

Binary insertion sort to sort the test suites based on the number of test cases in ascending order.

```
def binary_insertion_sort(A):
```

```
    for i in range(1, len(A)):
```

```
        current_suite = A
```

```
        num_of_testCases = current_suite['num_of_testCases']
```

```
        index = binary_search(A, num_of_testCases, 0, i)
```

A.pop(i)

A.insert(index, current_suite)

D. Test suites prioritization

The generation of test suites is an essential step in the software testing process. A well-designed test suite can help to ensure that all aspects of a software product are thoroughly tested, thereby reducing the risk of defects and bugs. The generation of test suites can be mathematically represented as follows:

Let us consider the following:

T is the set of test suites defined as $\{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$, where n is the total number of test suites to be used over the testing of the software products.

Within each test suite denoted as $T_i, i=1(1)n$, there is a collection of individual test cases represented as

$$CT_i = \{C_1(i), C_2(i), \dots, C_m(i)\} = \{C_j(i)\}, j=1(1)m \quad (2)$$

Where m is the number of test cases. It is not necessary that the different test suits may not have a similar number of test cases. The test cases may or may not differ from one test suit to another test suit.

The size of each test suite T_i , denoted as $SZ=|T_i|$, is computed on the basis of the number of test cases available in the test suite.

$$SZ=|T_i| = |CT_i| = m \quad (3)$$

The above equation represents that the size of a test suite is equal to the number of test cases within that suite. Once the size of each test suite has been determined, the next step is to sort the test suites in ascending order through binary insertion sort as represented below

$$T_i = \text{binary_insertion_sort}(T), i=1(1)n \quad (4)$$

This approach provides a structured method for arranging test suites. The test suites are sorted, and then their priority is determined using a binary search technique. With this method, testers may ensure that their test suites are thorough and efficient at finding errors and faults.

E. Test Suite Scheduling

After getting a sorted list of the test suits, a slicing technique is used to save time for the execution of the test suits over the modules of the software product which is defined by the use of the FIRST IN FIRST OUT(FIFO) algorithm [18].

```
# Use FIFO (First-In-First-Out) to run test suites
test_suite_queue = deque(test_suites)
next_testSuite = test_suite_queue.popleft()
test_suiteName = next_testSuite['name']
file_path = test_suites[test_suiteName]
print(f"Running test suite: {test_suiteName}")
```

The process starts with a "test_suite_queue" as a FIFO queue to manage test suite execution order, prioritizing suites with fewer test cases upfront. The loop continues until the queue is empty. In each iteration, the foremost suite is dequeued, named "next_testSuite." The suite's name is stored as "test_suiteName," and the file path is retrieved from the "test_suites" dictionary. After dequeuing, the code prepares for execution using the specified file_path. During execution, messages indicate the running test suite in the format: "Running test suite: {test_suiteName}." The loop continues until no pending test suites remain. All suites execute based on the prioritized FIFO queue.

Mathematically, execution can be represented as T_i represents test suites, and $n(t)$ represents the test case count in suite t . The test_suite_queue ensures a non-decreasing order of test case count, guaranteeing execution order based on prioritization ($n(t_1) \leq n(t_2) \leq \dots \leq n(t_n)$).

F. Testing Strategy

The test procedure is then carried out using a predetermined testing strategy once the test suite has been prioritized and scheduled using the binary search method. Test methods including unit testing, integration testing, regression testing, retesting, and more might be incorporated into this approach. In order to evaluate the software's quality and spot any possible problems, test reports should be produced and examined for the production of an efficient software product.

G. Result Analysis

Once the test cases are run, and the testing strategy has been successfully applied the outcome shall be analyzed with the production of the test results which are summarized in the form of reports emphasizing high-priority flaws that may be found in the first round of testing. The reports are helpful resources for decision-making, additional development, and troubleshooting and also for further testing.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Binary insertion sort is used in this study to evaluate the software's performance. During the testing process, this strategy optimizes the utilization of time and resources by prioritizing test suites for better problem exploration. Calculating performance measures and comparing them with established methods, verifies the effectiveness of the proposed model. Alongside the Binary insertion sort strategy, other well-liked techniques like ANN-Whale [19], AGC [20], and FEST [21] are also extensively tested. This review provides valuable information about the benefits and drawbacks that are considered to resolve the proposed method in comparison to existing methods.

A. Average percentage of fault prediction (APFD)

The goal of increasing a subset of the test suite's fault detection rate is measured using a statistic called APFD. The percentage of test suite execution that matches the fault detection rate is computed in this way. To calculate the APFD, the weighted average of the percentage of errors discovered during test suite execution is utilized. Greater APFD values correspond to faster and/or superior fault detection rates. The APFD value range is 0 to 100. The formula to compute APFD is given below:

$$APFD = 1 \frac{\left(\frac{CTC}{CT_i}\right)}{T_iS} \quad (5)$$

Where CTC is the Cumulative Test Cases (sum of test cases executed for each test suite), CT_i is the Total Test Cases (total number of test cases executed across all test suites), and T_iS the Number of Test Suites. APFD for a collection of test suites has been computed. The test suites, the number of test cases in each suite, and the percentage representation of the computed APFD values are shown in Table 1 below. More effective fault detection is indicated by APFD values that are closer to 100%.

TABLE 1. Computation of APFD for Test Suites

Test Suites	Test Cases	APFD (percentage)
test_suite_10	10	98.11
test_suite_3	20	95.85
test_suite_7	30	91.32
test_suite_9	40	81.13
test_suite_8	50	70.57

Test Suites	Test Cases	APFD (percentage)
test_suite_2	60	60.38
test_suite_6	70	51.32
test_suite_1	80	42.64
test_suite_4	90	34.34
test_suite_5	100	26.00

*APFD for test suites

As illustrated in Figure 1, there is a positive correlation between the size of the test suite and the efficacy of defect identification. The effectiveness of condensed testing is further demonstrated by more manageable test suites, like 'test_suite_10', which has 10 cases with impressive APFD rates (98.11%). This data highlights the importance of optimizing test suite architecture to provide more accurate mistake detection while controlling overall size.

FIGURE 2. Performance Chart for APFD with Different Test Cases

B. Execution Time

It is the calculation of the time required to complete the whole process. Also, the developed model takes a time period to minimize the test cases and identify the faults that are calculated for identifying the execution time that is calculated using eqn. (6)

$$X_t = \frac{\text{Start_time} - \text{end_time}}{\text{total_time}} \quad (6)$$

In general, the execution time should be low for an efficient approach. Our method's temporal evaluation is shown in Table 1 below.

TABLE 2. Computation of execution time taken by test cases

Execution time(s)		
Test_suites	Test Cases	BIS(Proposed)
test_suite_10	10	10.13
test_suite_3	20	10.72
test_suite_7	30	12.83
test_suite_9	40	17.37
test_suite_8	50	26.91
test_suite_2	60	29.77
test_suite_6	70	35.92
test_suite_1	80	41.13
test_suite_4	90	45.66
test_suite_5	100	52.67

*Execution time of test cases

Here, the existing methods require more time to complete the process but the developed manner utilized reduces the amount of time needed to finish the steps listed in Table 2. Furthermore, while processing 50 test cases, the current approaches, such as AGC, ANN-Whale, and FEST, use large execution times of 33.78 s, 42.45 s, and 35.78 s. Therefore, the proposed Binary insertion sort model – which is shown in Table 2 – achieved a shorter execution time of 26.91 seconds while performing 50 test cases, this is seen in Figure 2.

TABLE 3. Comparison of execution time

Test Cases	Execution time(s)			
	ANN-Whale	AGC	FEST	BIS(Proposed)
10	20.45	16.34	24.87	10.13
20	24.87	19.45	27.39	10.72
30	31.67	24.87	22.67	12.83
40	35.98	27.39	26.78	17.37
50	42.45	33.78	35.78	26.91

*Execution time comparison

FIGURE 3. Execution time comparison

C. Memory Utilization

The efficiency of the developed Binary insertion sort approach is computed based on resource utilization. The amount of memory used by the test cases in this scenario is measured in bytes. Table 4's contrasting values demonstrate that the recommended method of test case minimization required less memory during the operation. The memory needed should be as little as possible to achieve the efficient process that the suggested Binary insertion sort model does.

TABLE 4. Computation of memory utilization

Memory (Bytes)		
Test_suites	Test Cases	BIS(Proposed)
test_suite_10	10	495616
test_suite_3	20	507056
test_suite_7	30	651264
test_suite_9	40	684032
test_suite_8	50	720896
test_suite_2	60	770048
test_suite_6	70	929792
test_suite_1	80	983040
test_suite_4	90	1040384
test_suite_5	100	1728512

*Memory utilization calculation

TABLE 5. Comparison of memory utilization

Test cases	Memory (Bytes)		
	ANN	ANN-Whale	BIS(Proposed)
10	1,289,565	1,165,485	495,616
20	1,658,984	1,235,478	507,056
30	1,385,678	1,345,786	651,264
40	1,598,745	1,524,587	684,032

*Memory utilization comparison

The memory space utilization of existing methods like ANN and ANN-whale are compared with the proposed model. Also, the attained outcomes are graphically represented in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4. Evaluation of memory

4. CONCLUSION

Binary Insertion Sort (BIS), a technique that arranges test suites based on size, will be helpful in software testing. It takes just 26.91 seconds to finish 50 test cases, illustrating how BIS increases execution efficiency. It also consistently uses memory efficiently, especially when working with bigger test suites. The Average Percentage of Faults Detected (APFD) evaluation shows how successfully BIS finds important test cases. As evidenced by these findings, BIS is a valuable method for improving testing procedures and further study is recommended to assess the scalability of BIS in larger, complex testing environments. Comparative analysis with advanced techniques like ANN-Whale and AGC would provide insights into its broader applicability for diverse project sizes.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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